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Report on established training centres

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Abstract	This report presents a mapping of established training centres involved in research ethics, research integrity and/or public health that could be identified in Sub-Saharan Africa countries.
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Executive summary

This report presents findings on the mapping of established training centres in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), focusing particularly on Cameroon, Ghana and Mozambique. These centres can serve as access points and platforms for STRATEGIC aimed at raising ethical awareness and training on the review and evaluation of health technologies. In addition to the three focus countries, the mapping encompasses a total of 49 countries: Angola, Benin, Botswana, Burkina Faso, Burundi, Cabo Verde, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Chad, Comoros, Congo, Djibouti, DR Congo, Equatorial Guinea, Eritrea, Eswatini, Ethiopia, Gabon, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Lesotho, Liberia, Madagascar, Malawi, Mali, Mauritania, Mauritius, Mozambique, Namibia, Niger, Nigeria, Rwanda, Sao-Tomé-and-Principe, Senegal, Seychelles, Sierra Leone, Somalia, South Africa, South Sudan, Sudan, Tanzania, Togo, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe. The aim of this report is to provide an overview of relevant institutions in SSA that offer training programs, especially in the field of research ethics and integrity and/or public health, enabling subsequent STRATEGIC trainings in the field of ethics review and evaluation of health technologies. The findings of the mapping will inform the STRATEGIC project in developing enhanced training materials that effectively address existing gaps – such as financial barriers, lack of accessibility, and limited awareness. The report first discusses the methodological approach of desk research and online consultation, specifies identified training centres and discusses results from the validation phase. It concludes with an outlook on the next steps, covering the design of training materials and implementation in several of the identified training centres.

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List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ARIN	African Research Integrity Network
AU	African Union
EC	European Commission
EDCTP	European & Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership
ENERI	European Network for Research Ethics and Integrity
EU	European Union
EUREC	European Network of Research Ethics Committees
GHS	Ghana Health Service

ICT	Information and Communications Technology
INGO	International Non-Governmental Organisation
NEC	National Ethics Committee
NRA	National Regulatory Agency
RE	Research Ethics
RI	Research Integrity
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SSA	Sub-Saharan Africa
STRATEGIC	Sustainable eThics Reviews of digital heAlth Technology dEsiGn In sub saharan afriCa
LETS	University of Yaoundé I
LMIC	Low-and-Middle-Income-Countries
LUMSA	Libera Università di Roma
UEM	Universidade Eduardo Mondlane
UoN	University of Nottingham

Table 1: List of acronyms/abbreviations

Introduction

The STRATEGIC project aims at co-creating culturally sensitive responsible methods to strengthen existing ethics and regulatory capacities of digital health technologies in SSA.

The project aims to develop a theoretically grounded and empirically informed approach to Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), alongside a capacity-building plan and resources to strengthen ethics and regulatory institutions for clinical trials and research in SSA. This work is carried out in collaboration with European and African consortium partners who have extensive expertise in ethics reviews, research ethics, technology ethics, and clinical research and practice. The project emphasises the use of culturally sensitive and responsible methodologies, involving partners from English, French, and Portuguese-speaking countries, to enhance existing ethical and regulatory capacities for digital health technologies in SSA.

The overall objective of STRATEGIC is to jointly develop and test an ethically responsible, culturally sensitive and legally compliant approach to the regulation of digital health technologies in clinical research and practice in Africa, and to build the capacity of National Ethics Committees (NECs), National Regulatory Agencies (NRAs) and other key stakeholders to implement and embed the project approach.

This will be done, among other things, through the development and implementation of a sustainable training and awareness program in ethics and regulation of digital health technologies in SSA to improve efficiency and existing capacities.

To achieve this, we have divided our work into three phases:

DEVELOPMENT: We will familiarise ourselves with existing training centres, projects, initiatives, networks, etc. that are already addressing – in a broad sense – ethical and regulatory issues of health technologies. Building on this, we will develop training materials and implement training programmes that may be of interest to these actors by filling existing gaps in training needs.

INTEGRATION: Based on the participatory methodology developed in the STRATEGIC project, we will ensure that the training materials meet the needs of key stakeholders and collaborate with existing initiatives from both, Africa and Europe, such as the African Research Integrity Network (ARIN, <https://africanetwork.wixsite.com>) or the European Network for Research Ethics and Integrity (ENERI, <https://eneri.eu/>). This will allow us to reach key stakeholders in the field of health technology who are concerned with ethical and legal issues.

IMPLEMENTATION: To ensure usability of the developed training materials in existing training centres, we will test them at three sites with 10 members of NECs and NRAs. These members will in turn act as trainers to ensure the sustainability of the materials in a train-the-trainer programme.

This report on existing training centres provides an overview of the current status of institutionalised and national training capacities in SSA in the field of Research Ethics (RE), Research Integrity (RI), and/or public health. The report therefore aims to list all relevant actors, including universities, networks, projects, initiatives, and other organisations that could be involved in training on review and evaluation of health technologies within the framework of STRATEGIC. The following text outlines the initial phase of development, how the mapping of existing training centres was carried out as well as the results of the mapping process.

1. Methodology

1.1 Partner consultation

Three project partners, GHS, UEM, and LETS, located in Cameroon, Ghana and Mozambique contributed to the mapping of existing training centres and provided key insights based on established knowledge and contacts regarding institutions in their region. Through their inputs and networks, 28 institutions, along with one relevant individual, were identified in Cameroon, Ghana, and across the African Lusophone countries.

Partner consultation in this research project proved invaluable, as it fostered a collaborative approach that leveraged local expertise and contextual understanding, ensuring the relevance and accuracy of the findings. The diverse perspectives brought by the partners enriched the analysis and allowed for navigation of regional nuances more effectively.

Alongside the involvement of project partners, the acquaintance of former EUREC collaborators active in the RE and RI field in SSA facilitated the identification of additional four institutions across Africa (Ethiopia, Gambia, and two initiatives active continent-wide). This collaborative effort also enabled outreach to a considerably larger audience, as one external partner shared the online consultation survey with over 150 contacts in their network across Africa.

1.2 Desk research

To identify existing training centres in SSA, especially those in Ghana, Mozambique and Cameroon, collaborative desk research was started with the aim of compiling a collection of data through internet research. In this collaboration with consortium partners, an intensive form of cooperation and exchange was sought in order to bundle knowledge, generate synergies and benefit from the (local) expertise of the projects partners and jointly ensure the greatest possible overview of existing training centres. Desk research was conducted from May 2024 to August 2024 based on the following 3 steps:

1. Data from existing institutional websites, training documents and previous research (projects) related to health technology training as well as secondary data, such as curricula, has been explored to gather information over established training centres in SSA:

Use Google search:

- i. Country name +
 1. Research ethics training
 2. Digital health training
 3. Medical health training

If no training centre could be identified, this has been noted in the spreadsheet.

2. All identified contact points have been added to mapping spreadsheet. Identified training centres have been screened for one of the following key words:

*Technology

*Digital

*AI

*Electronic

*ICT

If one of the key words was found, this has been noted in the spreadsheet.

3. A separate tab on the spreadsheet lists only those training centres that could be prioritised due to focus on digital health technology training (Name of training centre, country, type of training offered)

In addition, the spreadsheet displays further details such as the type of institution, research focus, language (as represented on the website), entry contact point, scope (national or international), and prior involvement in EDCTP framework.

1.3 Online consultation

To validate desk research findings and to fill any existing gaps in the mapping of established training centres, an online consultation was conducted. This consultation was intended to identify further existing training centres through external, independent, individual contributions from already identified training institutions. The aim of the online consultation was to flag which institutions might have been overlooked throughout the desk research, or to exclude non-relevant organisations – hence validating initial findings from desk research. Online consultation was conducted from 30 August 2024 to 18 September 2024 based on the following 3 steps:

A questionnaire for the mapping of training centres in SSA, including 6 sections with a total of 15 questions has been developed, reviewed and approved by the project consortium (see appendix). The aim of the questionnaire was to find out which training centres on digital health technologies and/or ethical reviews currently exist in Sub-Saharan Africa, especially Cameroon, Ghana and Mozambique assessing the status quo on existing training centres and possibilities for further cooperation in the STRATEGIC project.¹ Questions about existing training centres and their programmes should be addressed in terms of a place where training is provided and where healthcare professionals, researchers, ethics reviewers or others can gain qualifications in digital health technologies. Questions about training centres therefore also include universities, ethics committees, online platforms and other organisations.

Ethics approval has been provided by UoN.²

¹ While the identified training centres generally focus on health, public health, or medicine, suggesting a potential inclusion of digital health technologies, this research has notable limitations. The information available on the centres' websites, as well as the articles and reports that informed this secondary data, was often insufficient or unclear, making it challenging to determine whether and how they address ethical aspects related to health technologies. Additionally, language barriers further complicated access to relevant content. To investigate and validate the findings of this mapping, direct outreach to the centres was conducted through an online consultation questionnaire.

² After partners have reviewed the online consultation survey, it has become evident that ethics approval will be necessary for NECs and NRAs in Ghana and Cameroon prior to answering the questionnaire. UoN provided ethics approval for this research activity on behalf of the project consortium.

The online questionnaire has been circulated among 384 contact points that have been identified during desk research.³ These contact points represent stakeholders who have been identified as relevant actors within STRATEGIC to potentially support the project consortium in mapping training centres in Sub-Saharan Africa. Of the 384 online questionnaires sent out, 25 answers were obtained.

1.4 Country cards

As part of this mapping, “country cards” were created, which are part of the annex to this report and display identified training institutions per country. In addition, the country cards provide training-relevant information such as the type of organisation, official national language, capital city and population. These country cards are planned to be displayed on the strategic website (<https://www.strategic-project.org/outputs>), designed to offer a user-friendly, visually appealing overview of the main findings of the mapping. The geographical focus of this research has been Sub-Saharan Africa as defined by the EU (cf. https://international-partnerships.ec.europa.eu/countries/sub-saharan-africa_en), covering 49 officially recognised countries (see Table 2: Geographic repartition of identified institutions).

³ The online survey has been circulated via direct link to Office Forms.

2. Findings

2.1 Identified training centres, projects, initiatives, networks & other institutions in SSA

Figure 1: Map of identified institutions

The mapping of established training centres was conducted in two stages: first, desk research which identified 466 institutions, 421 of which were in SSA countries, 22 covering the whole continent, 6 international organisations, such as the United Nations (UN) or the Pasteur Network which are non-governmental organisations, active on multiple continents, and 17 institutions and projects that were identified as relevant to the report but are only active in the European Union (EU). And secondly, the online consultation, through which 10 additional institutions could be identified (1 covering the whole continent, 1 international organisation and 8 in SSA countries). In total, a number of 476 training institutions has been identified.

Figure 2: Institutions suggested by⁴

Table 2 below (as well as country cards in the annex) provides an overview of the number of institutions per country and region (in alphabetical order) while Figure 1 above presents these findings through a geographical perspective for the whole of Africa. It is already possible at this stage to acknowledge the wide national disparities across the region regarding existing institutions.

Countries	Number of identified institutions
Angola	2
Benin	5
Botswana	4
Burkina Faso	4
Burundi	3
Cabo Verde	3
Cameroon	21
Central African Republic	3
Chad	1
Comoros	1
Congo	2
Djibouti	2
DR Congo	16
Equatorial Guinea	1
Eritrea	1
Eswatini	1
Ethiopia	26
Gabon	2

⁴ Not all institutions suggested by "external partners" were from the online consultation but also included secondary recommendations from previously identified stakeholders. Identification by "project partners" included all STRATEGIC consortium partners and was not limited to the three focus country representatives GHS, LETS and UEM.

Gambia	4
Ghana	24
Guinea	4
Guinea-Bissau	2
Ivory Coast	5
Kenya	28
Lesotho	1
Liberia	1
Madagascar	5
Malawi	4
Mali	4
Mauritania	1
Mauritius	4
Mozambique	15
Namibia	2
Niger	10
Nigeria	82
Rwanda	7
Sao-Tomé-and-Principe	1
Senegal	7
Seychelles	1
Sierra Leone	2
Somalia	17
South Africa	31
South Sudan	3
Sudan	12
Tanzania	17
Togo	4
Uganda	15
Zambia	10
Zimbabwe	8
African Continent	23
European Union	17
International Organisations	7

Table 2: Geographic repartition of identified institutions

In addition to providing an overview of the number of relevant institutions by country, which is of great importance to STRATEGIC as it allows the project to target institutions across the regions in terms of training while providing insights into the geographical gaps, this mapping also examined various additional aspects that were considered relevant. These aspects include: the type of institution, the expertise and research focus area of each institution, the languages being used (according to the source of data, e.g. institutional website); funding and/or regulation by national authorities, involvement in EDCTP frameworks. These specifics add further depth to the mapping and better reflect the complexity of digital health technology training infrastructures across SSA.

In the subsequent sections, mapping findings on these aspects are illustrated in graphics and briefly explained.

2.2 Identified training centres, projects, initiatives, networks & other institutions in Cameroon, Ghana and Mozambique

Figure 3: Map of identified institutions in focus countries

As part of the mapping exercise, three focus countries—Cameroon, Ghana, and Mozambique—were selected to represent SSA both geographically and linguistically. These countries exemplify the diversity within the region, encompassing Western (Cameroon), Central (Ghana), and South-Eastern Africa (Mozambique), as well as reflecting a range of linguistic contexts: Francophone, Anglophone, and Lusophone.

In total, 21 institutions were identified in Cameroon, 24 in Ghana, and 15 Mozambique, positioning these three focus countries among the top 10 SSA nations by the number of identified institutions. This prevalence can be partly attributed to the involvement of local partners—GHS, LETS, and UEM—who are established institutions within these countries. Their support provided a more nuanced and comprehensive local overview, facilitating the identification of training centres that may otherwise have been overlooked.

However, while these three countries offer valuable insights into the training landscape of SSA, it is important to consider their representativeness. The educational and training contexts in these countries may not fully encapsulate the diversity and challenges faced by all 49 SSA nations. Variations in governance, resource allocation, and socio-economic factors could result in significant differences in the availability and quality of training centres across the region. Therefore, while the findings from Cameroon, Ghana, and Mozambique contribute important perspectives, further research is necessary to capture the broader landscape of training institutions in Sub-Saharan Africa.

3. Discussion

3.1 Types of institutions

Figure 4: Types of institutions

Universities	A university is an institution of higher education dedicated to advancing knowledge through research, teaching, and study. It offers a wide range of academic programmes and professional training opportunities, equipping students with both theoretical knowledge and practical skills. Universities are authorised to award degrees such as Bachelor's, Master's, and Doctorates, which often include elements of specialised training.
Projects, networks, and initiatives	These are diverse groups, collaborations, or efforts across various sectors that aim to promote innovation, cooperation, and positive societal impact. They often provide training and capacity-building opportunities to enhance the skills of participants and stakeholders, fostering development in their respective fields.
Training centres	Training centres are dedicated facilities for enhancing the skills and knowledge of an organisation's staff through targeted education and development programmes. These centres focus on practical training,

	workshops, and courses to meet the specific needs of the organisation and improve workforce competencies.
Research centres	Research centres are specialised institutions that drive progress by exploring complex questions and generating new knowledge in various fields. They often offer training programmes, internships, and workshops to develop the research skills of students, researchers, and professionals, ensuring a continuous flow of qualified experts in their respective disciplines.
NECs and NRAs	NECs are key bodies responsible for upholding ethical standards in research, ensuring that studies are conducted transparently, ethically, and with respect for participants' rights. They often collaborate with NRAs to provide training on ethical conduct, RI, and regulatory compliance. This collaboration ensures that research involving pharmaceuticals, medical devices, and biological products adheres to both ethical standards and international regulations of quality, safety, and efficacy.
International and regional non-governmental organisations	An international non-governmental organisation (INGO) operates independently of the government and often provides training and capacity-building programmes to empower local communities, support development projects, and build expertise in areas such as human rights, education, health, and the environment on a global or regional scale.

To better capture the reality of institutions potentially relevant to STRATEGIC, data was collected on the various types of institutions represented, acknowledging that some do not fit neatly into a single category. Considering the various categories is important as it not only offers a clearer overview of the institutions involved in training, but also helps reach different audiences targeted by each organisation for future STRATEGIC capacity-building and training activities. As can be seen in Figure 4, the majority of institutions identified for this mapping are universities and higher education institutions (75%).

Additionally, 8% of the institutions are NECs or NRAs, 7% are projects, networks and initiatives, 4% are exclusively training centres, 4% are research centres and finally only 2% are international, regional or non-governmental organisations.

Even though all these institutions are involved in training on RE, RI and/or public health topics, they address very different target groups. Considering different target audiences in the STRATEGIC project for health technology awareness raising, training and capacity building is crucial, as it addresses diverse needs and perspectives, enhances learning outcomes, and promotes compliance. For example, tailored content can help healthcare providers focus on patient privacy concerns, while IT professionals may delve into data security issues. This approach strengthens interdisciplinary collaboration and fosters cultural sensitivity. This customisation is essential for promoting a comprehensive understanding and responsible use of digital health technologies.

3.2 Expertise & focus

Figure 5: Institutions expertise & focus

Since the mapping used as a point of reference the existing training in the areas of RE, RI and public health to assume a possible interest in training in review and evaluation of digital health technologies, the aspect of institutional expertise and focus area is considered in this section. Under the assumption that training in RE, RI, and public health is fundamentally interconnected with training in digital health technologies, capacity building, and awareness raising, institutions offering training courses in one or more of these subject areas have been considered in this mapping. This is because understanding ethical principles is crucial in the development and application of digital health tools, ensuring that they are used responsibly and align with ethical standards such as patient privacy, data security, and informed consent. Moreover, capacity building in digital health enables healthcare professionals to effectively use these technologies within broader public health frameworks, enhancing outcomes through data-driven decision-making and innovative health services. Additionally, awareness raising on ethical principles considering digital transformation promotes best practices, digital literacy, and equitable access to health technologies. Such training ensures that digital health innovations are grounded in sound research practices, adhere to ethical standards, and address the digital divide, thereby fostering trust and ensuring that technological advancements contribute meaningfully to public health goals of society. While the three focus areas have distinct emphases, they often interrelate and overlap in topics such as health policy and management, ethics in public health, confidentiality and data protection, vulnerable populations, data management, scientific misconduct, and openness and transparency. These and other areas are critical not only for ensuring ethical research and robust public health systems but also for training in review and evaluation of digital health technologies, where ethical considerations, data protection, and equitable access play a pivotal role, as they define the ethical, legal and practical parameters.

As already mentioned, the majority of the identified institutions are universities. All university institutions considered in this mapping offer public health programmes as part of their curricula, so that 85% of the identified institutions can be assumed to have expertise in the health sector and corresponding thematic areas, as can be seen in Figure 5. In addition, these institutions might also have ethics committees, which, if in place, could not be verified during desk research, unlike the public health training specified in university curricula.

A non-negligible proportion of the identified institutions (12%) have expertise in the area of ethics, bioethics and integrity, and thus have some focus on RE, RI and health issues, which in turn have relevance to the broader topic of digital health technologies.

Finally, 3% of the organisations identified could not be assigned to one or all of the specific subject areas public health or RE, RI, but were nevertheless included in the list of identified training institutions as they seem relevant in terms of capacity building and awareness raising in the field of digital health technologies as their trainings are aimed at, e.g. research managers, covering technology and innovation issues in applied sciences.

3.3 Languages

Figure 6: Institutions languages

The consideration of the different national languages is a central point in mapping existing training centres in SSA due to the impact on accessibility and usability to the future training materials of the project. In this mapping exercise, it was particularly important to determine which languages are official national languages in the respective countries, especially in Cameroon, Ghana and Mozambique, and which languages the identified institutions use to offer trainings.⁵

As can be seen in Figure 6, the majority of the identified institutions either use English only (66%) or offer English alongside other (mostly local national) languages (14%). Taking into account organisations that only provide information in French (16%) and Portuguese (3%), this leaves only 1% that use other languages such as Arabic, Spanish or German. It can therefore be concluded that almost all of the selected organisations are accessible in either English, French or Portuguese and that all countries in SSA have at least one organisation with accessible information in one of these three languages.

However, it is important to note that desk research was conducted in English and French, while online consultation was conducted only in English, which might have limited relevant findings of this mapping. Availability of

⁵ The indicator here was in particular the languages in which the individual websites were available.

valuable information about existing trainings in English, French or Portuguese does not always reflect the reality at local level, where many more languages are spoken. Only 17 of a total of 476 organisations (3%) made information available in at least one of the local languages of SSA countries. To reflect this, the STRATEGIC online consultation questionnaire asked about barriers to accessibility and support measures, e.g. language.

This information is of key importance for the STRATEGIC project, as it confirms that project training materials could be made available in English (and possibly in French and Portuguese), thus ensuring high accessibility and usability.

3.4 Governmental national institutions

Figure 7: Governmental national institutions

<p>Governmental national institutions</p>	<p>Governmental national institutions involve both the formal structures of governance and informal but influential entities. These institutions, along with civil society organisations, statistical agencies, and supranational and intergovernmental collaborations (such as the EU) and its institutions, e.g. the European Commission (EC)), provide training programmes and capacity-building initiatives. These programmes aim to enhance the skills and knowledge of public officials, policymakers, and civil society, fostering good governance practices, transparency, and effective public administration.</p>
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This mapping also considers which institutions are national governmental centres — i.e., institutions that are established, funded, and/or regulated by national authorities. The purpose of this identification is to determine which actors might hold the most power, based on the assumption that high-level governmental institutions have the most de facto influence (in comparison to, for example, regional non-governmental organisations). This is particularly relevant where top-down support for the implementation of training is crucial for its actual implementation. However, exploring this aspect has been challenging, as some institutions may be public without being national centres, such as universities. Moreover, there are considerable differences between individual countries, as some governments might be better equipped or more willing to invest in this area, while others are not.

Only a few (11%) of the identified institutions, mostly NECs, were listed as national government centres. This suggests that NECs may not be the most influential actors in digital health technology training and awareness-raising. Other national governmental institutions, such as ministries or major health organisations, might hold more authority and resources, overshadowing the influence of NECs. Furthermore, NECs might have a more specialised focus or limited mandate, making them less influential in broader policy discussions or training initiatives compared to larger governmental bodies. The effectiveness and influence of NECs can also vary by country, as some may not enjoy the same level of governmental support or recognition as other national centres. Therefore, engaging non-governmental organisations and other stakeholders is essential to reach a broader audience and enhance the overall impact of training initiatives.

3.5 EDCTP involvement

Figure 8: EDCTP involvement

EDCTP	The European and Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership (EDCTP) is a collaboration between the EU, Norway, Switzerland, low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), other donors, and the pharmaceutical industry to support clinical trials and
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	training for the development of new medical treatments, recognising the need for global action to reduce poverty.
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Given that STRATEGIC itself is part of the EDCTP framework, it was important to indicate which of the identified institutions are also involved in this programme and therefore familiar with relevant conditions that could be conducive to the STRATEGIC project, such as established networks, existing training materials, policy recommendations, etc. However, this aspect was difficult to capture during the mapping process, as not all organisations provide information that is up to date, or this information could not be found during desk research. Therefore, only those organisations that provided a clear and findable reference to the EDCTP framework were counted as being related to the programme in this mapping. Ultimately, only 13% could be counted as EDCTP-related under this criterion. Realistically, the actual number of organisations participating in EDCTP frameworks is assumed to be higher.

3.6 Focus countries

Figure 9: Types of institutions in the focus countries

As focus countries for the STRATEGIC project, particular attention has been placed on Cameroon, Ghana, and Mozambique in this mapping exercise to determine their representativeness and relevance for the future training processes of the project. These countries are represented in the project consortium, which facilitates in-depth insights and on-site training support in the organisation of training workshops. Their involvement ensures that the training processes are tailored to the specific needs and contexts of each country, thereby enhancing the overall effectiveness and applicability of the project outcomes.

Cameroon, Ghana, and Mozambique collectively house a notable array of training institutions, with 15, 21, and 24 institutions identified, respectively. This positions them as critical players in the educational landscape of Sub-Saharan Africa. However, it is equally important to extend the project's focus to regions with limited capacity, where targeted efforts in capacity building and awareness raising are essential to foster sustainable educational practices.

Figure 10: Institutions expertise & focus in the focus countries

Figure 11: National Centres in the focus countries

Figure 12: EDCTP involvement in the focus countries

Building upon the study of identified institutions in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), Figures 10 to 12 present a comprehensive overview of the institutions' focus and expertise, the proportion of national entities, and the number of institutions engaged in EDCTP programmes within the focus countries: Cameroon, Ghana, and Mozambique.

The data reveals that these three countries reflect the general trends observed across the SSA region, exhibiting similar proportions of institutions that are classified as national centres and those involved in the EDCTP framework programmes. However, a notable disparity is evident in Figure 10, which illustrates the focus areas of these institutions. Specifically, Mozambique demonstrates a higher prevalence of institutions specialising in ethics, bioethics, and research integrity questions, contrasting with Cameroon and Ghana, where the majority of institutions are oriented towards Health and Public Health.

It is important to note that these disparities in training focus areas do, however, not necessarily indicate a lack of interest or relevance in digital health technology training, as all identified focus areas are intrinsically linked to this topic. This suggests that the training landscape in these countries is diverse and reflects the multifaceted nature of health challenges faced in the region.

This overview reinforces the relevance and significance of the strategic focus on these countries. In addition to their geographical and linguistic representation of the SSA region, the mapping indicates that the existing institutions within Cameroon, Ghana, and Mozambique effectively reflect the broader landscape of training centres across SSA. By identifying these institutions, the study not only highlights the current capabilities within these countries but also informs future initiatives aimed at enhancing health training and capacity building in the region.

4. Validation

4.1 Online consultation⁶

The online consultation was shared with 387 institutions (the email address of 79 out of the 466 institutions could not be identified) and 3 relevant non-affiliated individuals.⁷

Out of the contacted institutions and individuals, 272 did not respond and 87 email addresses led to a mail delivery error. 25 representants completed the online consultation and one redirected us to a personal contact considered as more fitting. Furthermore, one representative of an institution forwarded, with our knowledge and consent, the consultation to over 150 of his personal contacts in SSA.

This online consultation provided our mapping with 10 additional relevant institutions that were included in our report which represent 3% of all identified institutions (against 88% identified through desk research, and 9% recommended by project partners). The consultation also validated 18 institutions that were already mapped during desk research. The 25 answers of the consultation covered 27 institutions (one respondent representing 3 institutions, another one two, and two respondents being from one single institution).

⁷ These individuals were recommended by project and external partners due to their expertise and therefore included to the consultation but not in the mapping itself.

Figure 13: Countries of the online consultation's respondents

The online consultation results reveal that respondents are fairly evenly distributed across SSA, representing 16 out of the 49 SSA countries, including West, East, Central, and Southern Africa. Additionally, there is one representative from a cross-African institution, and another based in Europe (see Figure 13).

The institutions identified through the online consultation correspond to the same countries as the location of the respondents, covering six SSA countries along with one international organisation and one that operates across the African continent. This confirms that the identified actors are primarily familiar with existing institutions at the local level in their respective countries (see Figure 14).

Figure 14 Institutions by country identified by the online consultation

The primary objective of the online consultation was to gather detailed information about training centres and institutions involved in digital health technology in SSA.

Figure 15: Do you know of any institution(s) in your region in Sub-Saharan Africa that may be suitable for conducting trainings on review and evaluation of digital health technologies?

Figures 16 to 22 provide detailed insights into the relevant training practices of each survey respondent, highlighting existing examples on the ground and the experts' participation habits in training (Figures 16 & 17). Figure 17 is particularly noteworthy, as it indicates that experts are more familiar with seasonal training programmes. Additionally, answers to the questionnaire offer valuable insights into potential strategies for developing and implementing STRATEGIC training materials and for identifying starting points for building personal and institutional contacts as part of future training programmes (Figures 15 & 18).

Figure 16: Have you already taken part in training courses at such a training institution?

Figure 17: How often are you taking part in training courses at a training institution?

Figure 18: Do you know of other organisations in Sub-Saharan Africa, such as projects, networks or other initiatives who are already involved or might be interested in training in digital health technologies?

The responses collected from the survey provide valuable insights into existing good practices and gaps in the provision of training programmes. For instance, they reveal pertinent information regarding the content of training programmes (as illustrated in Figure 19) and their formats (as shown in Figure 20). Notably, there is a significant gap in training related to data protection among the respondents. Additionally, face-to-face training formats emerged as the most commonly experienced method among participants.

These findings will be instrumental in shaping the development of new training courses, ensuring that they address the identified gaps—particularly in data protection—and incorporate effective formats that align with the needs of participants.

Moreover, the open-ended responses highlight key challenges faced by the respondents. The primary issues identified stem from a lack of accessible local training opportunities. Additionally, financial constraints were cited as the main obstacle to participation in training.

In response to these challenges, STRATEGIC aims to develop training materials and engage with local training centres identified through this mapping exercise. By addressing these issues, STRATEGIC seeks to enhance the

availability and relevance of training in the region, ultimately contributing to capacity building and skill development.

Figure 19: What types of training courses are offered by the training institution(s) or other types of organisation(s) you are aware of?

Figure 20: What training formats are offered by the training institution(s) or other types of organisation(s) you are aware of?

Are the training courses at the training institution(s) or other organisation(s) easily accessible (e.g. in terms of geographical location, equipment, language options)?

Figure 21: Are the training courses at the training institution(s) or other organisation(s) easily accessible (e.g. in terms of geographical location, equipment, language options)?

Are there other projects, networks, platforms, initiatives or individuals potentially relevant for STRATEGIC that you would recommend us establishing contact with?

Figure 22: Are there other projects, networks, platforms, initiatives or individuals potentially relevant for STRATEGIC that you would recommend us establishing contact with?

Overall, the online consultation served as a crucial validation of the partner consultation and desk research results, providing a solid foundation for the development of the STRATEGIC training materials. It complemented previous findings with more detailed information about training centres focused on digital health technology in SSA. The consultation not only identified additional relevant stakeholders for future training initiatives but also highlighted common and underrepresented training formats, existing barriers, and important content areas. As a result, future project efforts can be directed toward closing these gaps to ensure effective awareness raising, training and capacity building.

4.2 Take-away messages

A total of 476 training centres, projects, networks, initiatives, and other institutions were identified across SSA as potentially relevant for capacity building and awareness raising in the review and evaluation of digital health technologies. These institutions vary significantly in their target audiences, training capacities, and objectives, with specific focus areas that often interrelate thematically, particularly regarding ethical considerations in digital health technology. Notably, there are inequalities in the density and variety of training centres across the regions, influenced by factors such as population size and the predominance of universities and non-governmental

initiatives. Although facilities for training exist in every SSA country, English is the predominant language used, even in non-English-speaking nations, with local languages being almost entirely absent.

The results of the mapping show that the three focus countries reflect common patterns that can be observed in SSA and demonstrate the rationale of particularly addressing these regions with a dedicated training programme.

However, the project is recommended to broaden the scope and offer digital health technology training in countries that are less well equipped than the three focus areas, such as Eswatini, Chad, Eritrea or Liberia, which have the weakest training infrastructure according to the results of this mapping exercise, in line with the project mandate of capacity building and awareness raising.

In light of these findings, STRATEGIC should leverage this landscape through targeted training in areas where gaps exist. By connecting underrepresented regions with well-established ones, the project could enhance knowledge sharing. Universities, as primary training providers, could be instrumental in disseminating project materials. Additionally, organisations with fewer training offerings, such as INGOs and research centres, should be approached to assess their interest in utilising STRATEGIC materials to fill existing gaps.

Currently, most offered trainings are seasonal and conducted face-to-face, but it is unclear if this aligns with participants' preferences or if other formats might be more beneficial. A forthcoming STRATEGIC needs assessment will provide insights that can inform the design of training sessions. While financial barriers are noted as a challenge, the specifics of these barriers remain unclear; it is assumed that training costs and travel expenses contribute to the issue. By providing freely accessible training materials in English, with additional availability in French and Portuguese, STRATEGIC could enhance accessibility and usability for existing SSA training centres and initiatives, ultimately alleviating these constraints and expanding training opportunities.

5. Summary & outlook

In conclusion, this report has presented the results of mapping existing training centres, projects, networks, initiatives, and other institutions in SSA that are relevant to the STRATEGIC project and future capacity-building and awareness-raising activities. The identified entities either focus on digital health technologies or demonstrate a significant interest in the topic. This mapping has highlighted potential access points and platforms where project training materials could be integrated, hosted, and maintained over the long term. The results also provide a valuable overview for those interested in digital health training in SSA, making it easier to identify potential points of contact.

Through desk research and consultations, the mapping revealed that there are 476 training centres in SSA that meet the defined criteria. The findings indicate substantial potential for implementing a successful train-the-trainer program and deploying STRATEGIC training materials, given the diversity of institutions and their target audiences.

Moving forward, the disparities in training capacities identified across SSA will be considered when selecting appropriate training centres for future project activities. Furthermore, the specific training needs of various target audiences within different institutions will be considered during the development and implementation of training materials. It will be essential to conduct a needs assessment to determine the most effective training formats, as current assumptions on existing trainings may not align with participant preferences. Additionally, while barriers have been identified, further exploration is needed to understand their specifics. By addressing these considerations, STRATEGIC can better tailor its approach to effectively meet the diverse needs of interested parties in digital health technology training.

6. List of references

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2. Country cards as part of the STARTEGIC outputs, <https://www.strategic-project.org/outputs>.
3. European Network for Research Ethics and Integrity (ENERI), <https://eneri.eu/>.
4. Policy areas and specific objectives with Sub-Sahara Africa as The EU defines its policy areas and specific objectives with each partner country and region through the programming process. defined by the EU, https://international-partnerships.ec.europa.eu/countries/sub-saharan-africa_en.

7. Annex

1. Country cards
2. Online consultation questionnaire

STRATEGIC Country Cards

Established Training Centres in Sub-Saharan Africa

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Angola

Angola

#Institutions

2

Powered by Bing
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1. Universidade Agostinho Neto-Angola
2. Universidade Jean Piaget de Angola

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Luanda

Population: 35,159,000

Official languages: Portuguese

EDCTP

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Benin

1. Comité National d’Ethique pour la Recherche en Santé (CNERS)
2. Institut Régional de Santé Publique
3. Université d'Abomey-Calavi (UAC)
4. Université de Parakou
5. Richmond International University

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Porto-Novo

Population: 13,844,000

Official languages: French

EDCTP

Botswana

Botswana

#Institutions

4

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1. Botho University
2. Botswana International University of Science and Technology
3. Ministry of Health Research and Development Committee
4. University of Botswana

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Gaborone

Population: 2,413,000

Official languages: English

EDCTP

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Burkina Faso

Burkina Faso

#Institutions

4

1. Comité national d'éthique pour la recherche en santé (CNERES)
2. Université Joseph KI-ZERBO - Unité de Formation et de Recherche en Sciences de la Santé
3. Université Nazi BONI - Institut Supérieur des Sciences de la Santé
4. Université Saint Thomas d'Aquin

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

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Capital: Ouagadougou

Population: 23,409,000

Official languages: French

EDCTP

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Burundi

1. Hope Africa University
2. Université du Burundi
3. Université de Ngozi

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Burundi

#Institutions

3

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Capital: Bujumbura

Population: 13,439,000

Official languages: Rundi & French

EDCTP

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Cabo Verde

Cabo Verde
#Institutions
3

Powered by Bing
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1. Comité Nacional de Etica e Pesquisa em Saúde
2. Jean Piaget University of Cape Verde
3. Universidade de Cabo Verde

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Praia

Population: 491,100

Official languages: Portuguese

EDCTP

Cameroon I

Cameroon

#Institutions

21

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1. Biotechnology Centre of the University of Yaounde 1 (BTC)
2. Catholic University of Cameroon
3. Centre International de Reference Chantal Biya (CIRB)
4. Centre Pasteur du Cameroun
5. Centre for Research in Infectious Diseases (CRID)
6. Centre de Recherche pour la Santé des Armées (CRESAR)
7. Ecole des Sciences de la Santé (ESS-UCAC)
8. Fobang Institute for Innovations in Science and Technology (FINISTECH)
9. Higher Institute for Scientific and Medical Research (ISM)
10. Information, Communication and Technology (ICT) University
11. Institut Supérieur de Technologie Médicale (ISTM)
12. Research Centre on Emerging and Re-emerging Diseases (CREMER)
13. University of Bamenda
14. University of Buea
15. University of Douala
16. University of Dschang
17. University of Maroua
18. University of the Mountains
19. University of Ngaoundere
20. University of Yaounde 1
21. University of Yaounde 1 Digital Centre (UYI/CDNU)

Capital: Yaoundé

Population: 27,334,000

Official languages: English & French

EDCTP

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Cameroon II

Cameroon

#Institutions

21

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Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Yaoundé

Population: 27,334,000

Official languages: English & French

EDCTP

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Central African Republic

Central African Republic

#Institutions

3

1. EUCLID University
2. Institut Pasteur de Bangui
3. Université de Bangui

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Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Bangui

Population: 5,651,000

Official languages: Sango & French

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Chad

Chad

#Institutions

1

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1. Université de N'Djaména

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: N´Djamena

Population: 19,094,000

Official languages: Arabic & French

EDCTP

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Comoros

Comoros

#Institutions

1

1. Université des Comores

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Moroni

Population: 860,600

Official languages: Comorian, Arabic & French

EDCTP

Congo

Congo
#Institutions

2

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1. Comite d'éthique de la recherche en sciences de la santé
2. Université Marien-Ngouabi

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Brazzaville

Population: 6,373,000

Official languages: French

EDCTP

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Djibouti

1. Institut Supérieur des Sciences de la Santé (ISSS)
2. Université de Djibouti - Médecine Faculty

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Djibouti
#Institutions

2

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Capital: Djibouti

Population: 1,052,000

Official languages: Arabic & French

EDCTP

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DR Congo

DR Congo

#Institutions

16

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1. Comité national de bioéthique
2. Université de Bandundu
3. Université Catholique du Graben
4. Université Evangélique en Afrique
5. Université De Goma
6. Université de Kindu
7. Université de Kinshasa
8. University of Kisangani
9. Université Kongo
10. Université libre des Pays des grands lacs (ULPGL)
11. Université de Lubumbashi
12. Université Notre Dame du Kasayi
13. Université Officielle de Bukavu
14. Université Protestante du Congo
15. Université Shalom Bunia Faculté de Médecine
16. Université Simon Kimbangu

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Kinshasa

Population: 115,403,000

Official languages: French

EDCTP

Equatorial Guinea

Equatorial Guinea

#Institutions

1

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1. National University of Equatorial Guinea

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Malabo

Population: 1,669,000

Official languages: Spanish, French & Portuguese

Eritrea

Eritrea

#Institutions

1

1. Orotta School of Medicine

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Asmara

Population: 6,344,000

Official languages: None (de facto Tigrinya, English & Arabic)

EDCTP

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Eswatini

Eswatini

#Institutions

1

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1. University of Eswatini - Faculty of Health Sciences

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Mbabane & Lobamba

Population: 1,206,000

Official languages: Swati & English

EDCTP

Ethiopia I

Ethiopia

#Institutions

26

1. Adama Hospital Medical College (AHMC)
2. Adama Science and Technology University
3. Addis Ababa University
4. Addis Continental Institute of Public Health
5. Africa Medical College
6. Aksum University
7. Arba Minch University
8. Bahir Dar University
9. Bethel Medical College
10. Debre Berhan University
11. Debre Markos University
12. Haramaya University
13. Hawassa University
14. Hayat Medical College
15. Jimma University
16. Madda Walabu University
17. Mekelle University
18. Mizan Tepi University
19. MyungSung Medical College
20. National Bio-Ethics Committee
21. National Ethical Clearance Committee (NECC)
22. St. Medical College Paul's Hospital Millennium
23. The Armauer Hansen Research Institute (AHRI)
24. University of Gondar
25. Wollega University
26. Wolaita Sodo University

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Capital: Addis Ababa

Population: 109,900,000

Official languages: None (de facto Amharic)

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Ethiopia II

Ethiopia

#Institutions

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Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Addis Ababa

Population: 109,900,000

Official languages: None (de facto Amharic)

EDCTP

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Gabon

Gabon
#Institutions

2

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1. Comité National d'Ethique pour la Recherche (CNER)
2. Université Nationale du Gabon

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Libreville

Population: 2,430,000

Official languages: French

EDCTP

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Gambia

Gambia

#Institutions

4

1. Medical Research Council
2. Medicines Control Agency
3. The Gambia ERC project
4. The University of The Gambia

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Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Banjul

Population: 3,041,000

Official languages: English

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Ghana I

Ghana

#Institutions

24

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1. Accra College of Medicine
2. Accra Technical University
3. C. K. Tedam University of Technology and Applied Sciences (CKT-UTAS)
4. Cape Coast Technical University
5. Catholic University College of Ghana
6. Central University
7. Ensign Global College
8. Family Health Medical School
9. Garden City University College
10. Ghana Institute of Management and Public Administration
11. Ghana Technology University College
12. Ho Technical University
13. Kumasi Technical University
14. Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology
15. National Bioethics Committee of Ghana
16. Presbyterian University College
17. University of Cape Coast
18. University for Development Studies
19. University of Education, Winneba
20. University of Energy and Natural Resources

Capital: Accra

Population: 32,823,000

Official languages: English

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Ghana II

Ghana

#Institutions

28

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- 21. University of Ghana
- 22. University of Health and Allied Sciences
- 23. University of Mines and Technology
- 24. University of Professional Studies, Accra

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Accra

Population: 32,823,000

Official languages: English

EDCTP

Guinea

Guinea

#Institutions

4

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1. Comité national d'éthique pour la recherche en santé
2. Institut Pasteur de Guinée
3. Université Gamal Abdel Nasser de Conakry
4. Université Kofi Annan

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Conakry

Population: 13,990,000

Official languages: French

EDCTP

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Guinea-Bissau

Guinea-Bissau

#Institutions

2

1. CNEPS-Guiné-Bissau
2. National Institute of Public Health (INASA)

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Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Bissau

Population: 1,663,000

Official languages: Portuguese

EDCTP

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Ivory Coast

Ivory Coast

#Institutions

5

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1. Comité Consultatif National de Bioéthique de la République de Côte d'Ivoire
2. Institut Pasteur de Cote d'Ivoire
3. Université Alassane Ouattara
4. Université Felix Houphouet-Boigny
5. Université Nangui Abrogoua

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Yamoussoukro

Population: 32,065,000

Official languages: French

EDCTP

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Kenya I

Kenya

#Institutions

28

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1. Africa International University
2. Aga Khan University
3. Catholic University of Eastern Africa
4. Daystar University
5. Dedan Kimathi University of Technology
6. Egerton University
7. Great Lakes University of Kisumu
8. Jaramogi Oginga Odinga University of Science and Technology
9. Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology
10. Karatina University
11. Kenya Methodist University
12. Kenyatta University
13. Kisii University
14. Machakos University
15. Maseno University
16. Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology
17. Moi University
18. Mount Kenya University
19. Partners for Health and Development in Africa
20. Pwani University
21. South-Eastern Kenya University

Capital: Nairobi

Population: 51,563,000

Official languages: Swahili & English

EDCTP

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Kenya II

Kenya

#Institutions

28

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22. Strathmore University
23. Technical University of Kenya
24. Technical University of Mombasa
25. University of Eldoret
26. University of Kabianga
27. University of Nairobi
28. Uzima University

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Nairobi

Population: 51,563,000

Official languages: Swahili & English

EDCTP

Lesotho

Lesotho

#Institutions

1

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1. National University of Lesotho – Faculty of health sciences

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Maseru

Population: 2,120,000

Official languages: Sotho & English

EDCTP

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Liberia

Liberia

#Institutions

1

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1. University of Liberia A. M. Dogliotti School of Medicine

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Monrovia

Population: 5,498,000

Official languages: English

EDCTP

Madagascar

1. Comité d'Ethique auprès du Ministère de la Santé
2. Comité Malgache d'Ethique pour les Sciences et les Technologies
3. Institut National de Santé Publique et Communautaire
4. Institut Pasteur de Madagascar
5. Université d'Antananarivo

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Madagascar
#Institutions

5

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Capital: Antananarivo

Population: 30,854,000

Official languages: Malagasy & French

EDCTP

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Malawi

Malawi

#Institutions

4

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1. Malawi University of Science and Technology
2. Mzuzu University
3. National Health Sciences Research Committee
4. University of Malawi College of Medicine

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Lilongwe

Population: 20,271,000

Official languages: None (de facto English)

EDCTP

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Mali

Mali

#Institutions

4

1. Comité d'Ethique, Institut National de Recherche en Santé Publique
2. EHESP-Mali (Ecole des Hautes Etudes en Santé Publique du Mali)
3. Mali-University Clinical Research Center (UCRC)
4. Université des Sciences, des Techniques et des Technologies de Bamako – USTTB

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Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Bamako

Population: 23,948,000

Official languages: French

EDCTP

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Mauritania

Mauritania

#Institutions

1

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1. Faculté de médecine de Nouakchott

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Nouakchott

Population: 4,582,000

Official languages: Arabic

EDCTP

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Mauritius

Mauritius

#Institutions

4

1. Anna Medical College and Research Centre
2. National Ethics Committee of Mauritius
3. Sir Seewoosagur Ramgoolam Medical College
4. University of Mauritius

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Port Louis

Population: 1,235,000

Official languages: English

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Mozambique I

Mozambique

#Institutions

15

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1. Instituto Nacional de Saúde - Comité Institucional de Bioética para Saúde do INS
2. Instituto Superior de Ciências e Tecnologia de Moçambique
3. Pedagogical University of Maputo
4. Universidade católica de Moçambique - Comité Institucional de Bioética para Saúde da Beira
5. Instituto Superior de Ciências de Saúde - Comité Institucional de Bioética para Saúde do ISCISA
6. Faculdade de Medicina da Universidade Eduardo Mondlane - Comité Institucional de Bioética para Saúde da FM&HCM
7. Universidade São Tomás de Moçambique - Comité Institucional de Bioética para Saúde da USTM
8. Universidade Lurio - Comité Institucional de Bioética para Saúde da Unilúrio
9. Centro de Investigação em Saúde da Manhica - Comité Institucional de Bioética para Saúde do CISM
10. Hospital Provincial da Matola - Comité Institucional de Bioética para Saúde do HPM
11. Direcção Provincial de Saúde de Niassa - Comité Institucional de Bioética para Saúde de Niassa

Capital: Maputo

Population: 36,769,000

Official languages: Portuguese

EDCTP

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Mozambique II

Mozambique
#Institutions 15

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12. Direcção Provincial de Saúde de Tete - Comité Institucional de Bioética para Saúde de Tete

13. Direcção Provincial de Saúde e Gaza - Comité Institucional de Bioética para Saúde de Gaza

14. Direcção Provincial de Saúde da Zambézia - Comité Institucional de Bioética para Saúde da Zambézia

15. Mozambican National Bioethics Committee for Health

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Maputo

Population: 36,769,000

Official languages: Portuguese

EDCTP

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Namibia

Namibia

#Institutions

2

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1. Namibia University of Science and Technology
2. University of Namibia

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Windhoek

Population: 2,688,000

Official languages: English

EDCTP

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Niger

Niger

#Institutions

10

1. Centre de Recherche Médicale et Sanitaire
2. École Nationale de Santé Publique/Damouré Zika (ENSP/DZ)
3. École de Santé Publique et de l'Action Sociale (ESPAS)
4. Institut Pratique de Santé Publique
5. Institut de Santé Publique
6. Institut Supérieur de Santé
7. Université Abdou Moumouni
8. Université André Salifou - Faculté des Sciences de la Santé (FSS)
9. Université Africaine des Sciences Sociales Techniques et Médicales (UASTM)
10. Université Dan Dicko Dankoulodo de Maradi (UDDM) - Faculté des Sciences de la Santé (FSS)

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

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Capital: Niamey

Population: 26,292,000

Official languages: French

EDCTP

Nigeria I

Nigeria

#Institutions

82

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1. Abia State University
2. Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University
3. Adamawa State University
4. Adekunle Ajasin University
5. Adeleke University
6. Afe Babalola University
7. Ahmadu Bello University
8. Akwa Ibom State University
9. Ambrose Alli University
10. American University of Nigeria
11. Babcock University
12. Bayero University
13. Bells University of Technology
14. Benue State University
15. Bingham University
16. Bowen University
17. Center for Bioethics and Research
18. Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University
19. Covenant University
20. Crescent University, Abeokuta
21. Delta State University
22. Ebonyi State University
23. Edo State University Uzairue
24. Ekiti State University
25. Enugu State University Of Science And Technology
26. Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta
27. Federal University, Birnin Kebbi
28. Federal University, Lafia
29. Federal University, Lokoja
30. Federal University, Oye-Ekiti

Capital: Abuja

Population: 228,181,000

Official languages: English

EDCTP

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Nigeria II

Nigeria

#Institutions

82

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31. Federal University, Otuoke
32. Federal University of Petroleum Resources
33. Federal University of Technology, Akure
34. Federal University of Technology, Minna
35. Federal University of Technology, Owerri
36. Godfrey Okoye University
37. Gombe State University
38. Igbinedion University
39. Imo State University
40. Joseph Ayo Babalola University
41. Kaduna State University
42. Kwara State University
43. Ladoke Akintola University of Technology (Lautech)

44. Lagos State University
45. Landmark University
46. Lead City University
47. Madonna University
48. Michael Okpara University of Agriculture
49. Modibbo Adama University of Technology
50. Nasarawa State University
51. National Ethics Committee of Nigeria
52. Niger Delta University
53. Nile University of Nigeria
54. Nnamdi Azikiwe University
55. Novena University
56. Obafemi Awolowo University

Capital: Abuja

Population: 228,181,000

Official languages: English

EDCTP

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Nigeria III

Nigeria

#Institutions

82

57. Obafemi Awolowo College of Health Sciences, Olabisi Onabanjo University
58. Olusegun Agagu University of Science & Technology
59. Osun State University
60. PAMO University of Medical Sciences
61. Pan-Atlantic University
62. Prince Abubakar Audu University
63. Redeemer's University
64. Rivers State University
65. Sani Zangon Daura College of Health Technology
66. Tai Solarin University of Education
67. Umaru Musa Yar'Adua University
68. University of Abuja
69. University of Agriculture, Makurdi
70. University of Benin
71. University of Calabar
72. University College of Medicine, Ado Ekiti
73. University of Ibadan
74. University of Ilorin
75. University of Jos
76. University of Lagos
77. University of Medical Sciences, Ondo City
78. University of Maiduguri
79. University of Nigeria
80. University of Port Harcourt
81. University of Uyo
82. Usmanu Danfodiyo University

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Capital: Abuja

Population: 228,181,000

Official languages: English

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Nigeria IV

Nigeria

#Institutions

82

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Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Abuja

Population: 228,181,000

Official languages: English

EDCTP

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Rwanda

Rwanda

#Institutions

7

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1. Adventist University of Central Africa
2. Kigeme District Hospital
3. Rwanda Biomedical Centre (RBC)
4. Rwanda National Ethics Committee
5. Rwanda Standard Board (RSB)
6. University of Gitwe
7. University of Rwanda

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Kigali

Population: 13,833,000

Official languages: Rwanda, French, English & Swahili

EDCTP

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São-Tomé- and-Príncipe

São-Tomé-and-Príncipe

#Institutions

1

1. Universidade de São Tomé e Príncipe (USTP)

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: São Tomé

Population: 228,300

Official languages: Portuguese

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EDCTP

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Senegal

Senegal

#Institutions

7

1. Centre Régional de Formation, de Recherche et de Plaidoyer en Santé de la Reproduction (CEFOREP)
2. Conseil national de recherche en santé (CNRS)
3. Institut Pasteur de Dakar
4. Institut de Recherche en Santé, de Surveillance Épidémiologique et de Formation (iressef)
5. Université Cheikh Anta Diop
6. Université Gaston Berger
7. Université de Thies

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Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Dakar

Population: 18,504,000

Official languages: French

EDCTP

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Seychelles

Seychelles

#Institutions

1

1. University of Seychelles

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Victoria

Population: 105,000

Official languages: Creole, English & French

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Sierra Leone

1. Njala University
2. University of Sierra Leone

Sierra Leone

#Institutions

2

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Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Freetown

Population: 7,752,000

Official languages: English

EDCTP

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Somalia

1. Adal Medical University
2. Amoud University
3. Baresan University
4. Benadir University
5. East Africa University
6. Edna Adan University
7. Erdoğan Hospital

8. Frantz Fanon University
9. Gollis University
10. Hope University
11. Mogadishu University
12. Salaam University
13. Somali International University
14. Somali National University
15. University of Hargeisa
16. University of Health Science in Bosaso
17. University of Somalia

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

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South Africa I

South Africa

#Institutions

31

1. Africa Health Research Institute (AHRI)
2. Cape Peninsula University of Technology
3. Central University of Technology
4. Durban University of Technology
5. Education for Health Africa
6. Mangosuthu University of Technology
7. National Department of Health
8. Nelson Mandela University
9. North-West University
10. Rhodes University
11. Sefako Makgatho Health Sciences University
12. South African Medical Research Council Ethics Committee
13. South African Research Ethics Training Initiative IV (SARETI IV)
14. Southern African Research & Innovation Management Association
15. The National Health Research Ethics Council
16. Tshwane University of Technology
17. University of Cape Town
18. University of Fort Hare
19. University of the Free State

Capital: Pretoria, Bloemfontein & Cape Town

Population: 61,592,000

Official languages: Afrikaans, English, Ndebele, Pedi, Sotho, Swati, Tsonga, Tswana, Venda, Xhosa, Zulu & South African Sign Language

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EDCTP

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South Africa II

South Africa

#Institutions

31

20. University of Johannesburg
21. University of KwaZulu-Natal
22. University of Limpopo
23. University of Pretoria
24. University of South Africa
25. University of Stellenbosch

26. University of Venda
27. University of the Western Cape
28. University of the Witwatersrand
29. University of Zululand
30. Vaal University of Technology
31. Walter Sisulu University

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Pretoria, Bloemfontein & Cape Town

Population: 61,592,000

Official languages: Afrikaans, English, Ndebele, Pedi, Sotho, Swati, Tsonga, Tswana, Venda, Xhosa, Zulu & South African Sign Language

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EDCTP

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South Sudan

South Sudan
#Institutions
3

1. South Sudan Public Health Institute
2. University of Bahr el-Ghazal
3. University of Juba - School of Public Health

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Juba

Population: 15,254,000

Official languages: English

EDCTP

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Sudan

Sudan

#Institutions

12

1. Ahfad University for Women
2. Al Zaiem Al Azhari University
3. International University of Africa
4. National Health Research Ethics Review Committee, Department of Research, Ministry of Health
5. Neelain University
6. Nile Valley University
7. Omdurman Islamic University
8. Sudan University of Science and Technology
9. University of Gezira
10. University of Kassala
11. University of Khartoum
12. University of Medical Sciences and Technology

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Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Khartoum

Population: 47,653,000

Official languages: Arabic & English

EDCTP

Tanzania I

Tanzania

#Institutions

17

1. Africa Academy for Public Health (AAPH)
2. Ardhi University
3. Catholic University of Health and Allied Sciences
4. Hubert Kairuki Memorial University
5. Kampala International University in Tanzania
6. Kilimanjaro Christian Medical University College
7. Muhimbili University of Health and Allied Sciences
8. Mzumbe University
9. National Institute for Medical Research (NIMR)
10. Nelson Mandela African Institution of Science and Technology
11. St. Augustine University of Tanzania
12. St. Francis University College of Health and Allied Sciences
13. Sokoine University of Agriculture
14. State University of Zanzibar
15. Tumaini University Makumira
16. University of Dar es Salaam
17. University of Dodoma

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Capital: Dodoma

Population: 47,653,000

Official languages: Swahili & English

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Tanzania II

Tanzania

#Institutions

17

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Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Dodoma

Population: 47,653,000

Official languages: Swahili & English

EDCTP

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Togo

Togo
#Institutions
4

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1. Centre de Formation et de Recherche en Santé Publique
2. Comité Consultatif National de Bioéthique (National Bioethics Committee of Togo)
3. Global Wealth University
4. Université de Lomé

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Lomé

Population: 8,399,000

Official languages: French

EDCTP

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Uganda

Uganda

#Institutions

15

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1. Busitema University Faculty of Health Sciences
2. Clarke International University
3. Gulu University School of Medicine
4. Habib Medical School
5. Kabale University School of Medicine
6. Kampala International University School of Health Sciences
7. King Ceasor University
8. Kyambogo University
9. Makerere University School of Medicine
10. Mbarara University School of Medicine
11. National Bioethics Committee of Uganda
12. Soroti University School of Medicine and Health Sciences
13. Uganda Christian University
14. Uganda Martyrs University School of Medicine
15. Uganda Virus Research Institute (UVRI)

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Kampala

Population: 47,066,000

Official languages: Swahili & English

EDCTP

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Zambia

1. Cavendish University Zambia
2. Copperbelt University
3. Eden University
4. Levy Mwanawasa Medical University
5. Liutebm University

6. Lusaka Apex Medical University
7. Mulungushi University School of Medicine
8. Texila American University Zambia
9. University of Lusaka
10. University of Zambia

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Lusaka

Population: 20,856,000

Official languages: English

EDCTP

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Zimbabwe

Zimbabwe

#Institutions

8

1. Africa University
2. Bindura University of Science Education
3. Chinhoyi University of Technology
4. Great Zimbabwe University
5. Midlands State University
6. National University of Science and Technology
7. SADTAP Health Research Institute
8. University of Zimbabwe

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Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Capital: Harare

Population: 15,706,000

Official languages: Chewa, Chibarwe, English, Kalanga, Khoisan, Nambya, Ndau, Ndebele, Shangaan, Shona, sign language, Sotho, Tonga, Tswana, Venda, & Xhosa

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African Continent I

African Continent

#Institutions

23

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1. AccessAfrica
2. AccessAfrica2
3. Africa-Europe Science Collaboration and Innovation Platform (AERAP)
4. Africa Training Institute
5. AfricaCDC
6. African Research Integrity Network – ARIN
7. African Union - Health, Humanitarian Affairs and Social Development (HHS)
8. Ethics in Research and Clinical Practice (ETHIMED)
9. EthIXPERT
10. Institut Sous-Régional de Statistique et Économie Appliquée (ISSEA)
11. Kumasi Centre for Collaborative Research in Tropical Medicine
12. LusoAfro Bioethics
13. Organisation de Coordination pour la lutte contre les Endemies en Afrique Centrale (OCEAC)
14. Pan-African Institute of Research and Innovation (PIRI)
15. SEA-RAFES project (Strengthening and Enhancing the Réseau Africain Francophone d'Éthique en Santé)

EDCTP

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African Continent II

African Continent

#Institutions

23

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- 16. The African Academy of Sciences – AAS
- 17. The African Regional Training Centre – ARTC
- 18. The African Society for Laboratory Medicine – ASLM
- 19. The African Vaccine Regulatory Forum – AVAREF
- 20. UNICEF Eastern and South Africa
- 21. UNICEF West and Central
- 22. Université Senghor
- 23. WHO - African Region

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

EDCTP

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European Union I

European Union

#Institutions

17

1. BEYOND BAD APPLES Project
2. Health Network for Tuberculosis and HIV (CANTAM)
3. EACCR Network
4. EUREC Board
5. European Association of Research Managers and Administrators (EARMA)
6. Embassy of Good Science
7. ENERI Network
8. European University Association (EUA)
9. iRECs Project
10. Path2Integrity Project
11. PREPARED Project
12. ROSiE Project
13. TESA: Trials of Excellence in Southern Africa
14. The African coalition for Epidemic Research, Response and Training (ALERRT)
15. V-Research
16. VIRT2UE Project
17. WANETAM: West African Network for Tuberculosis, AIDS and Malaria

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European Union II

European Union

#Institutions

17

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Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

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Cross-continental institutions

1. Pasteur Network
2. The Global Health Network
3. TRD Special Programme for Research and Training in Tropical Diseases
4. TRREE
5. United Nations
6. USAID
7. VolREthics Initiative

Types of Institution

- Universities & higher education
- Research centres and institutes
- Projects, networks & initiatives
- NEC and NRA
- Training centres
- International, regional non-governmental organisations

Cross-continental institutions

#Institutions

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EDCTP

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STRATEGIC Online Consultation on Existing Training Centres in Sub-Saharan Africa

Dear participants,

This questionnaire was developed within the STRATEGIC project (www.strategic-project.org). STRATEGIC is a research project funded by the European Commission that aims to co-create a theoretically sound, empirically based and widely consulted approach to responsible research and innovation, as well as a plan and capacity building materials that can strengthen the relevant ethics and regulatory institutions for clinical trials and research in sub-Saharan Africa.

The aim of this questionnaire is to find out which training institutions on digital health technologies currently exist in sub-Saharan Africa, especially Mozambique, Cameroon and Ghana, and to test training materials developed in STRATEGIC at existing training centres. STRATEGIC focuses on digital health technologies for clinical trials and research, such as e-consent platforms, wearable devices and biosensors, big data and advanced analytics, Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning, clinical trial management systems and others.

The questionnaire comprises 15 questions to assess the status quo on existing training centres and possibilities for further cooperation. Questions about existing training institutions and their programmes should be addressed in terms of a place where training is provided and where healthcare professionals, researchers, ethics reviewers or others can gain qualifications in digital health technologies. Training centres can therefore also include universities, ethics committees, online platforms and other organisations.

The questionnaire was sent to stakeholders who have been identified as relevant actors within STRATEGIC to potentially support the project consortium in mapping training centres in sub-Saharan Africa.

The data we collect will be treated in strict confidence.

If you have any questions or suggestions regarding STRATEGIC, please contact info@strategic-project.org.

The STRATEGIC project consortium

Personal Information

1. Please provide your name and affiliation, as well as any other contact details you would like to share:

Awareness and utilisation

2. Do you know of any institution(s) in your region in Sub-Saharan Africa that may be suitable for conducting trainings on review and evaluation of digital health technologies?
 - Yes
 - No
3. If you answered "Yes" to the previous question, please indicate the name and address of the training institution(s) here:
4. Have you already taken part in training courses at such a training institution?
 - Yes
 - No
5. If you answered "Yes" to the previous question, can you please indicate how often?
 - Daily
 - Weekly
 - Monthly
 - Seasonal
 - Yearly
 - Never
 - I don't know
 - Other
6. Do you know of other organisations in Sub-Saharan Africa, such as projects, networks or other initiatives who are already involved or might be interested in training in digital health technologies?
 - Yes
 - No

7. If you answered "Yes" to the previous question, please indicate the name and contact details of the organisation here:

Training courses offered

8. What types of training courses are offered by the training institution(s) or other types of organisation(s) you are aware of?
- Basics of research ethics
 - Research integrity
 - Specific training on clinical trials
 - Training on data protection
 - Ethical issues in health technologies
 - Other
 - I don't know
9. What training formats are offered by the training institution(s) or other types of organisation(s) you are aware of?
- Face-to-face training
 - Guided online training
 - Free paced online courses
 - Hybrid training (a mix of onsite and online training)
 - Whole day courses or weekend courses
 - Other
 - I don't know

Accessibility and support

10. Are the training courses at the training institution(s) or other organisation(s) easily accessible (e.g. in terms of geographical location, equipment, language options)?
- Yes
 - No

11. If you answered "No" to the previous question, please specify encountered challenge(s) here:
12. What support (e.g. financial support, time flexibility) would be helpful to facilitate participation in training?

Additional resources and co-operations

13. Are there any collaborations between National Ethics Committees/National Regulatory Agencies and training institution(s) or other organisation(s) in your region in Sub-Saharan Africa that you consider particularly useful?
14. Are there other projects, networks, platforms, initiatives or individuals potentially relevant for STRATEGIC that you would recommend us establishing contact with?
- Yes
 - No
15. If you answered "Yes" to the previous question, please provide further contact details here: